

Information and Quantum $\exp(ipx)$ - The Importance of X Information

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If one considers a system of interactions based on impulse hits without time being a consideration, then it seems that p (momentum) could represent information. If this is so, $2p$ would represent double the information of p and a possible probability would be: $\exp(C p)$. A particle with constant p , however, has constant velocity and so $P(x)dx=dx/L$, where L is length, for any p . Furthermore, if p is said to represent information, then x should also represent information from a given origin. This would imply an $\exp(C1 x)$ probability.

Finally, in one dimensional reflection-refraction of a particle with rest mass from a $V1-V2$ interface, where $V1$ and $V2$ are constant potentials and E is the same on each side, one might suggest that even though p changes, overall intrinsic information linked to p and possible x should remain constant. This suggests "other" information based on probabilities to reflect and refract. If p values differ at a $V1-V2$ junction point, then one may use the product px with $x=0$ to remove information differences in the different p values at the $V1-V2$ junction. This then leads to the quantum free particle probability $\exp(ipx)$. By having x present, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ip(x+\text{phaseshift}))$ may interfere.

Time Independent Picture

In Newtonian mechanics, one considers $x(t)$ and so both x and t are intertwined. Nevertheless, Newtonian mechanical ideas (two particle elastic collisions) may be applied to an equilibrium in which there is no time present. Alternatively, given that impulses are based on p (momentum) and $p=m1v1=m2v2$, one does not need to know v and hence time to create an impulse based picture. Thus, we suggest considering a time-independent scenario involving p changes (or constant p motion).

Constant Momentum

The simplest time independent scenario is that of constant p within a length L . If one has the same rest mass, then different p values represent different times in each dx , but:

$$P(x)dx= dx/L \quad ((1))$$

This suggests that different p values have the same information using information = $\ln(P(x))$ if there is no clock in the picture.

One might, however, argue that p itself represents information and that $2p$ represents twice the information. If this is the case, then the same argument should hold for x .

Given that $\ln(P(x)) = -\ln(L)$, this information is essentially linked to the length, i.e. that is the information. Thus, p and x information have been removed, but it seems that they do represent information.

A question may arise: How does one remove information in order to create one probability from another? It seems that this is done frequently in statistics. For example, there may be a probability for red balls and another variable in a system and a probability for green balls and the same variable. Knowledge about ball colour and its link to probability is fine, but one may coarse grain this scenario and simply create a probability for a ball (regardless of colour) and another variable. Thus, $P(x)dx=dx/L$ not containing p or x is fine, it is simply a probability which has removed p and x . One may seek a probability containing p and x , such that it yields ((1)) under certain conditions.

One may next ask: If p and x both represent information, should they represent separate probabilities? We consider this question in the context of one dimensional reflection-refraction.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction for a Particle with Rest Mass

In such a case: $p_1 p_1^{1/2m} + V_1 = p_2 p_2^{1/2m} + V_2$ ((2)) nonrelativistic

V_1 holds for $x < 0$ and V_2 for $x > 0$

Given that m , rest mass, is the same in both regions and E is the same, from an energy point of view there is no change in information between an incident, reflected and refracted particle. From the point of view of p , however, there are information changes. The only x that appears is at the V_1 - V_2 junction point. Furthermore, there is now a new probability, namely that to reflect and refract.

We suggest that even though p and x may represent information separately, given that E is the same, it would be good to have intrinsic information linked with p to be the same. The only x information in the picture is $x=0$ and we suggest that this special value (which may always be chosen by positioning the origin at the V_1 - V_2 interface) may be used to create an intrinsic information using p and x such that this information is the same for the incident, reflected and refracted particle. Thus:

$$\text{information} = \ln[\exp(C_2 p x)] \quad ((3))$$

By using $x=0$, this information $C_2 p x$ is 0 for the incident, reflected and refracted particles and so the weightings of the probability $\exp(C_2 p x)$ may be used to create the real information in this problem.

Furthermore, $\exp(C_2 p x)$ allows one to make a link with ((1)) because $\exp(C_2 p x) \exp(-C_2 p x) = 1$. In other words, removing motion by using an AND with p and $-p$ yields the uniform $P(x)=1/L$.

For this scheme to hold, one then wants to have continuity of $\exp(C_2 p x)$ and its first derivative at $x=0$. One may see that $x=0$ removes the probability $\exp(C_2 p x)$ completely from the picture, i.e.

$$A \exp(C_2 p_1 x) + B \exp(-C_2 p_1 x) = C \exp(C_2 p_2 x) \quad \text{at } x=0 \quad ((4a)) \text{ and}$$

$$Ap_1 \exp(C_2 p_1 x) - p_1 B \exp(-C_2 p_1 x) = C_2 \exp(C_2 p_2 x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((4b))$$

The full information is linked with A,B,C, the coefficients of the incident, reflected and refracted particles as well as the p values. $x=0$ is not relevant as part of the information because the $V_1=V_2$ interface may be anywhere.

We point out, however, that this does not mean that x does not represent information. It does in $\exp(C_2 p x)$ as $\ln(\exp(C_2 p x)) = C_2 p x$. This x information is experimentally manifested in phase shift interference.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction and $x < 0$

We argued above that $x=0$ is a special interface point that allows for p_x to be the same for the incident, reflected and refracted particles. We also argued that $\exp(-C_2 p x) \exp(C_2 p x) = 1$ which is related to $P(x)$. To make the probabilities orthogonal in x , one may use $C_2 = i$. This ensures conservation of momentum in x .

We next consider a $P(x)$ analogue to ((4a)), namely:

$$AA + BB + 4BA \cos(2px) = P(x) \quad ((5))$$

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ implies a region \hbar/p in which x is uncertain. Even though $x=0$, there is still uncertainty within \hbar/p of $x=0$ and one does not know whether one has an incident or reflected particle. We suggest that this lack of knowledge is very important because it allows $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx)$ to interfere within one wavelength of $x=0$.

We note the analogy with two-slit interference with the slit distances being about \hbar/p apart. We suggest that an incoming object may interact with either one slit or the other because one cannot pinpoint the particle at any specific x within a wavelength. Using $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability and only using the knowledge that one has:

$$\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \quad ((6)) \text{ where } r_1 \text{ is from slit 1 to a point on the screen and } r_2 \text{ from slit 2. } R_1 \text{ and } r_2 \text{ are vectors.}$$

It is the lack of discernment of the two slits which allows for interference. One may say that a particle goes through one slit or the other, but this is a weak statement because one cannot discern through which slit it passes. We suggest that the same lack of information occurs for the incident and reflected particles within one wavelength of $x=0$.

What happens, however, far from $x=0$? We suggest the $\exp(ipx)$ represents the incoming particle at all times. For x far to the left of $x=0$, one has an early time with no reflected particle. Similarly, when the particle reflects and travels more than one wavelength away from $x=0$, there is no longer an incident particle for a single particle interaction. Thus, we caution taking the $\cos(2px)$ term too seriously when one is more than one wavelength away from $x=0$ for a single particle. $\cos(2px)$ in this case integrates to 0 showing that one has a mix of two momenta which are not conserved, i.e. p and $-p$. One does not change into the other.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may use the idea of information = $\ln(\text{Probability})$ to obtain the quantum form $\exp(ipx)$ if one makes use of the idea that both p and x are information, i.e. $2p$ is double the information of p and $2x$ of x . A product px allows one to use $x=0$ to make $px=0$ for any p . Thus even though one may have different p values, px at $x=0$ is the same for each. This puts the different px values on the same footing for $x=0$. We suggest that there is a special problem, namely one dimensional reflection-refraction of a particle with rest mass, which has the same E and rest mass for V_1 constant $x < 0$ with p_1 and V_2 constant for $x > 0$ with p_2 . Given that E and rest mass are the same for all x , it seems like the particle passes through $x=0$ without any information change from an energy point of view. If one wishes the same intrinsic information to be the same for p , one may use $px = \text{information}$ with $x=0$ as the special interface point. This does not mean that overall information is the same at the junction point because there is a different probability to reflect and refract. We suggest, however, that one may create $\exp(ipx)$ as being an intrinsic probability such that this and its first derivative is continuous at $x=0$, namely ((4a)) and ((4b)). Using $x=0$ essentially removes the px information from the problem leaving p and A,B,C weights linked to the incident, reflected and refracted particles.

If one wishes to have a probability with both p and x because there exists the probability $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length. In this expression, there is no direct p or x information suggesting that this probability has removed it in some way. We suggest that way is: $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$.